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Recommendations for standardization – M24

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I EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Description of the deliverable content and purpose

In Europe, one of the most emitting sectors is transportation: today trucks, buses and coaches are responsible for more than 25% of the greenhouse gases emissions from road transport in the European Union (EU) and for over 6% of total EU greenhouse gases emissions [1]. RHeaDHy project aims to support the reduction of transportation emissions by enabling the development of hydrogen heavy-duty vehicles (HDV) refueling infrastructure. **In this deliverable, RHeaDHy partners used their respective experience and work to share recommendations to the heavy-duty hydrogen mobility industry.** In this deliverable, the RHeaDHy project goals and current progress are explained, recommendations for the design of high-flow stations and vehicles are formulated, and more general guidelines and advice for the development of high-flow refueling hydrogen ecosystem are provided.

Indeed, in the wake of PRHYDE project¹ which focused on developing high-flow refueling protocols, RHeaDHy project aims to develop a high-flow refueling line and its components in order to test the new high-flow refueling protocols and unlock the construction of appropriate infrastructure for hydrogen HDV. More precisely, **RHeaDHy main goals are** the following:

- **Development of high-flow components and a high-flow refueling line:** design and build valves, heat exchanger, flowmeter, cooling system and dispenser such that it can fuel 100 kg in 10 minutes, reaching a maximal flow of 300 g/s. The station should be reliable and have reasonable energy consumption.
- **Extensive testing of refueling line:** test prototype dispensers on two sites equipped each with a test bench representative of truck tank system with ~100kg hydrogen capacity. Different high-flow refueling protocols will be implemented and used during the extensive test campaign.
- **Facilitating fast deployment of the high-flow stations:** certify developed components and ensure RHeaDHy dispenser will fit the market needs and existing and future standards, thanks to active participation of its members in standardization working groups, constitution of a project advisory board and active communication with the hydrogen mobility ecosystem.

RHeaDHy project began early 2023 and involves nine partners: ENGIE Lab CRIGEN, HRS (Hydrogen Refueling Solutions), ZBT (Zentrum für BrennstoffzellenTechnik), FORVIA (Faurecia), LAUDA, ALFA-LAVAL, EMERSON TESCO, EMERSON MICROMOTION, BENKEI. The project has currently focused on specifying the dispenser components and truck storage test system; on designing the prototypes and on building and testing the valves, heat-exchanger, flowmeter and chiller and pumps of cooling system. The next steps in 2025 are the dispenser assembly and programming and finally the extensive test campaign.

Some main guidelines, attention points and findings gained from partners past experience and from the first steps of specification, design and test preparation of RHeaDHy project have been summarized as recommendations for the hydrogen mobility ecosystem:

Recommendations for high-flow refueling station design

- **Station pressure drops should be minimized** to allow rapid refueling, a high state-of-charge (SOC) at the end of the refueling and optimal use of high-pressure storage (see 5.1). Therefore, all components and piping should be designed to allow high flow. It is recommended to target:

¹ see www.prhyde.eu

- **Maximum pressure drop of 70 bar between storages outlet and PCV** when at 200 g/s, 15°C, and 300 bar pressure at the PCV outlet (while fully opened)
- **Maximum pressure drop of 45 bar between PCV and receptacle (included)** when at 200 g/s, - 30°C, and 300 bar pressure at the PCV outlet

To reach such pressure drop values, all components should be specifically designed for high-flow refueling.

- **Communication between station and vehicle during refueling should be implemented** (see 5.2). Today, communicating optional data in SAE J2601-5 (TVL, FM) can allow to significantly reduce refueling time. Tomorrow, bi-directional communication could further increase performance and safety of refueling, by allowing some new protocols, such as the PRHYDE protocols, to be implemented.
- Refueling line **flowmeter should be chosen to be suitable for the dynamic process and flow range conditions** covered by the hydrogen refueling (see 5.3).
- To have a cost-effective, energy-efficient and compact cooling system, **it is recommended to minimize the installed chiller capacity and use a buffer storage** to cover peak cooling needs (see 5.4).
- **It is recommended to optimize the cascading** to maximize the efficiency of the storages. To achieve this, the number of cascades has a big influence **especially at the end of the refueling as more cascades helps in utilizing the stored hydrogen more efficiently** and consequently increase final SOC or back-to-back capacity (see 5.5).

Recommendations for high-flow vehicle design

- As for stations, **vehicle pressure drops should be minimized** to allow rapid refueling, a high state-of-charge at the end of the refueling and optimal use of high-pressure storage (see 6.1). It is recommended to target SAEJ2601-5 recommendations: maximum 15 MPa of pressure drop in the entire hydrogen vehicle line (receptacle excluded) when at 100 bar in the vehicle, - 15°C, and flow of 200 g/s.
- As for stations, **communication between vehicle and stations should be implemented during refueling** (see above in recommendations for stations and 6.2).
- **Temperature development in vehicle tanks should be carefully studied and measured.** To avoid overheating, thermal heterogeneities in both horizontal and vertical tanks should be limited via judicious tank and injector design (see 6.3), and temperature measurement sensor(s) should be positioned thoughtfully to be representative of the bulk temperature (see 6.4).
- It is also recommended to work on **common connection design** to bring better interchangeability and reliability to connections (see 6.5).

Recommendations for hydrogen mobility industry and standardisation committees

- **Hydrogen refueling protocols should be explained and described as precisely as possible** (see 7.1). **It is recommended to have some shared free tools and common list of tests to check their implementation** (see 7.2). Having a high level of detail and transparency and being able to check proper implementation are key to increase protocol adoption and ensure the refueling reliability and safety.

- It is also **recommended to focus on testing, improving and disseminating existing protocols** rather than on developing new approaches that will not lead to a significant performance gain (see 7.3).
- **Hydrogen leak tests should be conducted on each hydrogen component**, including tests with dynamic temperature variations similar to what occurs during component normal use (see 8.1). Moreover, **there is a need for hydrogen testing facilities** to conduct these appropriated hydrogen leak tests and high-flow tests more easily. Indeed, it is sometimes challenging to find appropriate testing infrastructure for new hydrogen products, which can slow the adoption of hydrogen solutions (see 8.2).
- Finally, **it is not recommended to put calibrated orifices in hydrogen stations when legally and technically possible** if – and only if - other mitigation measures are proved as valuable to limit maximum flow in case of critical event. Indeed, they can be very detrimental to performances (see 8.3).

Contacts for each partner organization can be found on RHeaDHy website: www.rheadhy.eu. For general enquiries, please reach to ENGIE (coordinator) and BENKEI.

2 Glossary

CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamic
CGH ₂	Compressed Gaseous Hydrogen
EU	European Union
FAT	Factory Acceptance Test
FM	Flow rate Maximum class: maximum flow allowed during refueling (in g/s)
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HDV	Heavy-Duty Vehicle
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
NWP	Nominal Working Pressure: Gauge pressure that characterize typical operation of hydrogen tank. It corresponds to a full tank (SOC = 100%) when temperature is 15°C.
OD	Optional Data: Optional Data field as defined in SAE J2799 v2.
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OTV	On-Tank Valve
PCHE	Printed Circuit Heat Exchanger
PCV	Pressure Control Valve
PRR	Pressure Ramp Rate
SAT	Site Acceptance Test
SOC	State Of Charge
TIR	Technical Informative Report
TSTS	Test Storage Truck System: Test bench constituted of a vehicle hydrogen storage system: multiple tanks, check valves, piping, sensors, receptacle, that will be refuelled during the RHeaDHy test campaign.
TV	“Total Volume”: Total volume of all the tanks in the vehicle (or TSTS)
TVL	“Tank Volume Large”: Volume of the largest tank of the vehicle (or of the TSTS)

3 Introduction

“Rapid and far-reaching transitions across all sectors and systems are necessary to achieve deep and sustained emissions reductions and secure a liveable and sustainable future for all”, stated IPCC in 2023 [2]. To target more specifically transportation CO₂ emission reduction, RHeaDHy project aims to support development of hydrogen heavy-duty vehicles (HDV). Indeed, to be widely adopted, hydrogen trucks should reach performance parity with diesel trucks. In particular, refueling should be fast: around 10 minutes. However, there is today a lack of high-flow stations allowing to fuel quickly large hydrogen heavy-duty vehicles. In the wake of PRHYDE project which focused on developing high-flow protocols, **RHeaDHy project aims to develop a high-flow refueling line and its components, in order to test the new high-flow refueling protocols and unlock the construction of appropriate infrastructure for hydrogen HDV.** It brings together nine partners, having expertise in refueling line components design and manufacturing, station assembly, testing, simulation, hydrogen truck design and innovation management, in order to achieve the following goals:

- **Develop high-flow components and a high-flow refueling line** tailored to refuel hydrogen Heavy-Duty vehicles.
- **Test the hydrogen fueling line** extensively, with relevant hydrogen refueling protocols
- **Ensure fast deployment** of the high-flow stations at the end of the project

RHeaDHy project started early 2023, and from the first steps of specification, design and test preparation, **RHeaDHy consortium gained a better understanding on high-flow refueling topic. This report aims to share the main recommendations and attention points that struck us as important to develop high-flow hydrogen refueling.** It can be noted that the recommendations in this report are **mainly based on partners experience and on simulations** as RHeaDHy dispenser is not built and tested yet. **By the end of the project, a second report will complement this one to specify and update the recommendations based on future test results.**

First, RHeaDHy project goals and current progress will be introduced. Then recommendations for high-flow refueling stations will be listed, followed by recommendations to take into account when building hydrogen tank truck systems. Finally, recommendations for protocols development and more general attention points for the hydrogen mobility industry will be pointed out.

4 RHeaDHy project goals and progress

4.1 Origin of RHeaDHy project

As reminded by the last IPCC report, global warming is today a major concern, and “**rapid and far-reaching transitions across all sectors and systems are necessary to achieve deep and sustained emissions reductions and secure a liveable and sustainable future for all**” [2]. In particular in Europe, one of the most emitting sectors is transportation: today **heavy-duty vehicles (HDV) are responsible for more than 25% of the greenhouse gases emissions from road transport, which is over 6% of total European Union greenhouse gases emissions** [1]. **Hydrogen is one of the promising ways to decarbonize this sector**, and reach the ambitious European objective of reducing the CO₂ emissions of new heavy-duty vehicles by 90% in 2040 compared to 2019 levels [1].

To be widely adopted, **hydrogen trucks should reach performance as close as possible to the one of current diesel trucks. In particular, refueling should be fast: around 10 minutes.** However, as of today, existing hydrogen refueling stations are not really adapted to heavy-duty vehicles: the refueling flow is too low (and consequently refueling time too high), the state of charge at the end of the refueling is sometimes not satisfying, and refueling protocols for heavy-duty vehicles are not yet mature and spread.

PRHYDE project (Protocol for heavy-duty Hydrogen refueling)² was a previous European project tackling this topic. It took place between January 2020 and September 2023, and achieved to **develop innovative high-flow refueling protocol concepts to fill heavy-duty hydrogen vehicles** that are detailed in the public final report *D6.7: PRHYDE results as input for standardisation* [3]. Additionally, SAE International issued the Technical Informative Report (TIR) **SAE J2601-5** [4] **in early 2024**. This document presents the first publicly specified high-flow refueling protocols that are based on current SAE J2601 [5] for light-duty vehicles and on PRHYDE project work, and allow to fuel heavy-duty vehicles up to 300 g/s without advanced communication.

However, PRHYDE resulted in mainly conceptual work and simulations and only **limited testing was conducted because of the lack of available appropriate equipment and suitable stations.** For the same reasons, SAE J2601-5 was initially published as a TIR and not as a SAE standard because of limited field testing. Thus, it appeared clearly that there was a gap in terms of hardware allowing high-flow refueling. Especially, **high-flow components allowing up to 300 g/s are needed to be able to implement high-flow protocols in real life.**

This is the main goal of the RHeaDHy European project, that started in February 2023. **RHeaDHy aims to develop a high-flow refueling line, and therefore associated high-flow components, in order to test the new high-flow refueling protocols and unlock the construction of appropriate infrastructure for hydrogen HDV.**

² see www.prhyde.eu

4.2 Goals of RHeaDHy project

More precisely, RHeaDHy main goals are the following:

- **To develop a high-flow refueling line tailored to refuel hydrogen Heavy-Duty vehicles.**
 - Develop or co-develop the sub-equipment needed to build a 300 g/s dispenser: heat-exchanger, chiller unit, pressure control valve, shut-off valves, break-away, nozzle and receptacle, hose, communication interface.
 - Develop and build a refueling line able to fuel a 100 kg truck in 10 minutes.
 - Maintain reasonable energy consumption.
 - Ensure station reliability.
- **To test the hydrogen fueling line extensively, with relevant hydrogen refueling protocols**
 - Develop specific fueling test bench that is representative of future hydrogen trucks and modular, with a maximum hydrogen capacity around 100 kg.
 - Deploy the RHeaDHy dispenser on two different sites.
 - Implement the new high-flow refueling protocols and give return of experience to industry.
 - Conduct an extensive test campaign (more than one year for each site) to get extensive feedback in various refueling conditions.
- **To ensure fast deployment of the high-flow stations at the end of the project:**
 - Standardise and certify the components of the station developed in the project.
 - Maintain a reasonable overall cost of the station.
 - Contribute to standard development through participation to standardization working groups.
 - Communicate actively with the hydrogen mobility ecosystem to be sure the refueling line fit the market needs.

Note: RHeaDHy project focuses on the 300 g/s dispenser. Compressors or high-pressure storages development / sizing / improvement are not in the scope of the project.

4.3 RHeaDHy partners

RHeaDHy gathers nine partners from three different European countries.

Figure 1 - RHeaDHy partners map

- **ENGIE Lab CRIGEN**

ENGIE is a global reference in low-carbon energy and services that strives every day to accelerate the transition towards a carbon-neutral economy, through reduced energy consumption and more environmentally friendly solutions. Inspired by its purpose statement, ENGIE reconciles economic performance with a positive impact on people and the planet, building on its key businesses (gas, renewable energy, services) to offer competitive solutions to its clients.

Coordinator of RHeaDHy project, ENGIE Lab CRIGEN, its research and innovation center, explores advanced energy technologies in many fields. Particularly, it contributes to the development of hydrogen production, storage, and distribution solutions to support the energy transition.

- **HRS (Hydrogen Refueling Solutions)**

HRS is originally an industrial piping company, that got specialised first in the fabrication, and then in the conception and installation of innovative hydrogen refueling solutions since 2009. HRS have already installed 28 stations through Europe and United Arab Emirates, and now owns a large new facility that has a capacity of production of 180 stations/year.

In RHeaDHy, HRS uses its experience in hydrogen station development to design and assemble the high-flow dispenser. HRS will also test one of the two RHeaDHy prototype on their test zone.

- **ZBT (Zentrum für BrennstoffzellenTechnik)**

ZBT is a publicly funded research institute with a focus on fuel cells and hydrogen. ZBT works on the entire value chain, from production to the application of hydrogen, including efficient and safe distribution and hydrogen refueling station concepts.

ZBT operates a hydrogen test field that has already been used for multiple research and industry projects. ZBT will take advantage of their experience to lead the organisation of the RHeaDHy test campaigns, and they will be in charge of testing one of the prototype refueling lines.

- **LAUDA**

LAUDA, the world market leader in precise temperature control, is a German company that has several decades of experience in designing and manufacturing high-performing plant engineering systems that provide heating and cooling power. LAUDA is already providing solutions to cool hydrogen compression systems and hydrogen dispensers.

In RHeaDHy, the LAUDA engineering team is responsible for designing the high-flow refueling cooling system to be as robust, reliable and energy-efficient as possible. Their experience with light duty Hydrogen Refueling Stations will provide very relevant insights on how to design a heavy-duty cooling system to fulfil the goals of this project.

- **ALFA LAVAL**

Alfa Laval is a French company that uses its 40 years of experience in heat transfer to develop, manufacture and service compact welded heat exchangers. Alfa Laval focuses in creating highly efficient heat exchangers to reduce and improve energy consumption of systems leading to CO2 emission reductions.

ALFA LAVAL contributes to RHeaDHy project by designing and optimizing the heat exchanger that will be positioned in the dispenser. Indeed, hydrogen cooling is necessary to reach expected refueling duration.

- **EMERSON TESCO (EMERSON-T)**

EMERSON TESCO designs and manufactures a wide range of standard and custom engineered pressure control regulator and valve solutions for a diverse, global market. EMERSON TESCO provides expert application and customer support for simple industrial applications or highly complex projects for a wide range of industries needed superior pressure control.

In RHeaDHy, EMERSON TESCO is in charge of developing shut-off valves and a pressure control regulator that fits the needs of a very high-flow refueling line.

- **EMERSON PROCESS Management Flow B.V. (EMERSON-M)**

EMERSON Process Management Flow B.V. (EMERSON-MICROMOTION) is expert in mass flow, density and viscosity measurement technologies. It delivers superior flow measurement expertise, while providing customers the confidence and insight they need to continuously improve accuracy, efficiency and safety in the most critical fiscal and process applications.

Based on knowledge gained from experience in flow measurement and understanding of the refueling needs with the consortium, EMERSON MICROMOTION will develop a state-of-the-art Coriolis mass flow meter that excels under the challenging conditions in terms of pressure and flow rate imposed by RHeaDHy project.

- **FAURECIA (FORVIA)**

Faurecia, (Group FORVIA), is a global automotive technology leader. Faurecia has made sustainable mobility a strategic priority and has a clear roadmap to develop hydrogen storage solutions adapted to different use cases. FORVIA Group covers 75% of the hydrogen drivetrain value with hydrogen storage systems, as well as fuel cell stack systems through Symbio, its joint venture with Michelin and Stellantis.

As a recognized Type-IV Composite tank and complete CGH2 storage system designer and manufacturer, Faurecia is supporting the demonstration of RHeaDHy high-flow dispenser for Heavy duty application by developing and delivering two test storage tank systems (TSTS) sized to onboard up to 100 kg of hydrogen at 70 MPa.

- **BENKEI**

Benkei is an innovation consulting company. Benkei assists its clients, both public and private, in the definition, implementation and evaluation of their innovation strategy. It favours co-development approaches and long-lasting collaborations, through missions specifically designed for their clients.

In RHeaDHy, Benkei's key role is to manage the communication, dissemination, exploitation & standardisation actions and to assist the coordination team to manage the whole project.

- **External Partners**

RHeaDHy is also working with external partners. For instance, external partners are providing high-flow break-aways, hoses, nozzles, receptacles, station filters. Partnership with Toyota to test twin nozzle solution was also set up recently. Moreover, discussions are currently ongoing to test innovative communication solutions or to conduct various high-flow refueling of pilot trucks from OEMs.

Contact for each partner organization can be found on RHeaDHy website: www.rheadhy.eu. For general enquiries, please reach to ENGIE (coordinator) and BENKEI.

4.4 Current progress

RHeaDHy project started early 2023. The first phase of the project consisted in understanding the needs and use cases for a high-flow dispenser, to specify requirements for the dispenser components and for the test storage truck system, to produce the high-flow components and to start preparing the test campaign.

Figure 2 – RHeaDHy achievements from the project start

Accomplishments of the project so far have been:

→ Specification of dispenser and components

In order to meet RHeaDHy ambitious goals of fueling 100 kg hydrogen vehicles in 10 minutes, an important work of specification of the complete dispenser and TSTS and of their individual components have been conducted. Especially, pressure drops should be minimized so that high flows can be reached in the fueling line. Using partners experience and numerical simulations, pressure drops specifications were established for the whole dispenser and TSTS, and then broke down into specifications for the various components. Moreover, cooling specifications were carefully drafted – also based on numerical simulations – in order to ensure sufficient cooling to reach desired performance at all seasons. Finally, special attention was drawn to interfaces, to ensure components compatibility in the final product.

→ Design and production of components

Once specifications were available, components such as shut-off valves, pressure control valves, chiller modules, heat-exchangers, flowmeters, TSTS were designed. Simulations and testing were performed to ensure that the desired specifications were met.

In particular, the following prototypes were produced:

- EMERSON TESCO developed and built a pressure control regulator and shut-off valves with 1" inlet and outlet ports. A special internal gas path design enables high flow rates up to 300 g/s hydrogen and very low pressure drops.
- EMERSON MICROMOTION designed and built high-flow flowmeter allowing to measure hydrogen up to 300 g/s with sufficient accuracy to meet station standards, and with very low pressure drops.
- ALFA LAVAL designed and built printed circuit heat exchangers (PCHE) with 132 plates and 8.3m² exchange surface that will allow quick cooling of hydrogen during refueling and high fatigue resistance.
- LAUDA designed and built cooling systems composed of two chillers and a pump module allowing to cool the heat transfer fluid down to - 45°C, with low GPW refrigerant (GWP2 and GWP6). A cold storage vessel allows to increase the peak cooling capacity up to 310 kW, while baseload cooling capacity is only 120 kW.

- FORVIA designed and is building two modular TSTS, each composed of six tanks with two different sizes. Maximum hydrogen capacity is 98 kg, and it can be reduced by closing some tanks manually. The system was designed to minimize pressure drops, especially by choosing relevant manifolds and pipe diameter.

→ **Adaptation of test sites layout**

The two test sites that will host RHeaDHy extensive test campaigns are at ZBT (Germany, Duisburg) and at HRS (France, near Grenoble). However, to be able to refuel the TSTS with the new dispensers, some layout adaptations are needed. In particular, both sites had to increase their storage capacity. In order to find the best compromise between cost and performance, various simulations have been conducted to test different storage and cascade configurations. Moreover, RHeaDHy plans to recycle as much of the hydrogen as possible used during the tests, both for cost and environmental reasons. Therefore, after each test fueling, the TSTS will not be vented, but defueled back into the station storages. An important work about the defueling line design is thus being conducted by RHeaDHy partners, in order to ensure safety and best possible performance for this defueling process. Finally, layout drawing to fit dispenser, storage, cooling and TSTS in the existing test zones while respecting safety constraints were also done.

→ **Anticipation of high-flow protocol to use**

RHeaDHy also studied the refueling protocols that will be needed to reach its goals. Based on partners experience and insights gained by participating in standardization committees (ISO, SAE), it has been decided to test extensively SAE J2601-5, and to compare it to PRHYDE protocols. Simulations were done to test what results these protocols would give when applied by RHeaDHy dispenser to fuel the TSTS. The envisioned performance is satisfying and RHeaDHy is confident the project goals will be met. The protocols implementation is currently ongoing. Depending on arising opportunities, other protocols may also be tested.

→ **Constitution of a stakeholders advisory board**

An advisory board has been established. This board brings together key stakeholders from hydrogen mobility industry to review the project's progress, assess ongoing results, validate technical approaches and guide strategic discussions. Thus, this advisory board helps ensuring that the project meet industry needs and tackles its upcoming challenges.

• **Next steps**

Next steps of the project to be conducted in 2025 and 2026 are to assemble the dispenser from the high-flow components provided by the partners, then to install it on the test stations together with the cooling system and TSTS, and finally to start the test campaign in order to assess the dispenser performance extensively.

From the first steps of specification, design and test preparation, **RHeaDHy consortium gained a better understanding on high-flow refueling topic. Some main guidelines, attention points and findings have been summarized below** as recommendations for the hydrogen mobility ecosystem.

5 Recommendations for high-flow refueling stations design

5.1 Minimize pressure drop in the station

It is recommended to minimize pressure drop in the station. This is a necessary condition for:

- Rapid refueling
- High State-of-Charge at the end of the refueling
- Optimal use of high-pressure storage

Therefore, all components and piping should be designed to allow high flow. It is recommended to target:

- **Maximum pressure drop of 70 bar between storages outlet and PCV** when at 200 g/s, 15°C, and 300 bar pressure at the PCV outlet (while fully opened)
- **Maximum pressure drop of 45 bar between PCV and receptacle (included)** when at 200 g/s, - 30°C, and 300 bar pressure at the PCV outlet

Pressure drops in the vehicle should also be minimized (see 6.1)

Explanations:

When studying high-flow refueling process to draft specification for the requirements, pressure drops appeared to be the main obstacle to overcome to manage fast refueling. Therefore, it was important for RHeaDHy project to understand the impact of pressure drop in order to draft relevant specifications for all the components of the refueling lines. It was mostly studied via simulations using HyFill tool.³

The next paragraphs will illustrate the impact of having large pressure drop on a refueling. First, a reference refueling with low pressure drops will be simulated. Then, it will be compared to simulated refuelings with increased pressure drops in various points of the line, to show they can be very detrimental for refueling performances.

Thus, on Figure 3 below, a reference refueling of a 100 kg truck storage system is simulated using MC-formula SAE J2601-5 protocol with ending pressure tables method. The station used for this refueling respects the recommended maximum pressure drops.

Note: For all the simulations shown in the document:

- Only the main fueling time is simulated.
- Initial pressure is 50 bar.
- Ambient temperature is 15°C.
- Cooling temperature is - 30°C.
- Temperature is supposed perfectly controlled (equal to target precooling temperature from 30 s after start of refueling –this hypothesis is acceptable for our purpose as small fluctuations

³ HyFill is ENGIE 0D-ID refueling validated model. See [11] and [3] for more information on this model.

that will happen in reality around target temperature will not impact significantly fueling time nor pressure drops.)

- Except if mentioned otherwise, cascades⁴ used are: two cascades of nominal working pressure (NWP) 500 bar with 76 kg hydrogen each, and eight cascades of NWP 950 bar with 40 kg each (it is an example, not the cascades set-up that will be implemented for RHeaDHy testing). Switch between cascades is considered instantaneous.
- Except if mentioned otherwise, the truck storage system contains 98 kg hydrogen when full. Its largest tank volume is between 350 and 800 L. Small pressure difference between the various tanks of the system due to a different piping path in the truck storage system is neglected.

Figure 3 -Refueling simulation results – Reference case. On the top are plotted interesting pressures: pressure of the high-pressure tank currently being used (black), pressure setpoint given by the protocol (magenta), dispenser simulated pressure (cyan) and vehicle tank pressure (blue). On the bottom is plotted the calculated mass flow rate. Final SOC is 98%, reached in 8 min and 5 sec.

Here, the refueling stops because the communication pressure target is reached. Final SOC⁵ of the vehicle tanks is 98%, reached in 8 minutes and 5 seconds. The performance of this refueling is very satisfying, as the final SOC is superior to 95% and the refueling time is less than 10 minutes.

Pressure drops used in this simulation are the recommended values:

- 70 bar between storages outlet and PCV when at 200 g/s, 15°C, and 300 bar pressure at the PCV outlet (while PCV is fully opened)
- 45 bar between PCV outlet and receptacle (included) when at 200 g/s, - 30°C, and 300 bar pressure at the PCV outlet.

⁴ A cascade is defined as a group of station storage tanks that have the same pressure and are opened and closed together to refuel the vehicle.

⁵ HyFill model also computes the temperature heating in the vehicle and station tanks during the refueling, even if not plotted here. Temperature and pressure knowledge allow to compute SOC.

- 150 bar between receptacle (excluded) and vehicle tanks, when at 200 g/s, - 15°C and 100 bar in the vehicle tanks, as recommended by SAE J2601-5 section A.3.2.8.

In order to better understand why it is so important to keep the pressure drops at a minimum, some simulations were also conducted with higher ones, to show their impact.

Downstream part from PCV outlet to vehicle tanks

Downstream pressure drop includes station pressure drops after the PCV and vehicle pressure drops. Both should be minimize. Indeed, the effect of having too much pressure drops after PCV can be very impactful. On the following figure, total pressure drop is increased compared to reference case: downstream station reference pressure drop and vehicle reference pressure drops are doubled.⁶ It can seem a lot to double the reference pressure drop, however it can very easily be reached with non-suitable components. For instance, only switching a high-flow shut-off valve by a typical shut-off valve currently used in H70 stations designed for 60 g/s or 90 g/s would multiply station side pressure drop by three at the reference point (200 g/s, 300 bar at PCV, - 30°C). And switching from high-flow break-away to typical current 700 bar break-aways designed for 60 g/s or 90 g/s refueling will make it impossible to reach this operating point used as reference – 200 g/s flow cannot be reached through such break-away. On the truck size, using unsuitable filters or manifolds can also drastically increase pressure drops.

Figure 4 - Refueling simulation results – high downstream pressure drops: the refueling is in the same conditions as reference refueling except it has increased downstream pressure drops. Final SOC is 81% and fueling time is 8 min and 5 sec. Here, refueling stops because there is no more storage with pressure high enough to fuel the TSTS. It can be estimated that if more storage was available, final SOC would be around 83% as dispenser pressure is only 10 bar from the limit pressure.

The two main effects of having more pressure drop in the refueling line can be seen here:

- **Larger downstream pressure drops increase the needs in high pressure storage.** As shown in Figure 4, increased pressure drops result here in premature stop of the refueling. While the storage configuration was previously sufficient to finish the refueling (see Figure 3), it is now insufficient due to the larger pressure drops. Indeed, when there are more pressure

⁶ Station downstream pressure drops are multiplied by two at the given reference conditions (200 g/s, 300 bar at PCV, - 30°C) and vehicle pressure drops are multiplied by two compared to SAE J2601-5 requirements operating points. The ratio might then change at other operating points.

drops in the line, higher upstream pressure is necessary to reach the same vehicle pressure. Thus, more hydrogen at high pressure is needed to complete a refueling with large pressure drops refueling line. In this example, there is not enough high pressure hydrogen to meet this increased need so the refueling stops earlier; additional storage would be necessary to finish the fueling. Of course, the impact of final SOC shown in these simulations is very dependent on the exact chosen configuration and total hydrogen amount in storages. However, the conclusion that more high-pressure capacity is needed for the same refueling when pressure drops are larger is generic: pressure drops have an impact on station refueling capacity that can be seen on large vehicles or back-to-back refueling. **This has an impact on cost** as more storage will be needed for the same final performance when pressure drops are higher (high-pressure tank storage additional cost, larger footprint necessary, ...)

- **Increased downstream pressure drops leads to smaller final SOC.** Indeed, in the case of large downstream pressure drops, the dispenser will reach its pressure limit while the vehicle pressure is still quite far from the dispenser pressure, as it can be seen on Figure 4. Thus, even if the fueling had not been stopped because of the lack of available storage, the final SOC would have been around 83%. This is **not really satisfying for customers**. On the contrary, when pressure drops are reasonable, the vehicle pressure catches up with the dispenser pressure at the end (see Figure 3), leading to a satisfying final SOC.

It can be noted that SAE J2601-5 introduced the “PRR Taper” method (Pressure Ramp Rate method) to limit the impact of high pressure drops on the refueling final SOC. Simulation of the same refueling as in Figure 5 (increased downstream pressure drops) but activating PRR Taper option is shown below.

Figure 5 - Refueling simulation results – high downstream pressure drops with PRR Taper option: the refueling is in the same conditions as reference refueling except it has increased downstream pressure drops. SAE J2601-5 PRR Taper option is on. Final SOC is 91% and fueling time is 9 min and 35 sec.

This refueling shows that **PRR Taper is very effective to improve the final SOC when there are large pressure drops**. Here, with the same hypotheses (pressure drops, station storage configuration), the final SOC is increased by 10 percentage points, which is very significant. However, **using PRR Taper results in an increased refueling time**. In this situation, refueling is 1min and 30 seconds longer which seems quite acceptable given the 10% SOC increase and the fact that total refueling time is still below 10 minutes. Finally, it can be underlined **that even with PRR Taper, the need for high pressure storage is still higher than in the reference case**. Once again, it is the

lack of hydrogen storage left that causes the refueling to stop. Thus, it is confirmed that high pressure drops leads to an extended use of high-pressure storage, which results in larger high-pressure storage needs and therefore higher cost.

This is why it is recommended to keep downstream pressure drops at their minimum. For the vehicle, RHeaDHy targeted the SAE J2601-5 recommendation (see 6.1). For the downstream part of the station – from PCV outlet to receptacle - 45 bar of pressure drop when hydrogen flows at 200 g/s, - 30°C and 300 bar at PCV seems a demanding but reachable target for the refueling. For instance, at this operating point, pressure drop can be split among major components as:

- ≤ 1 bar pressure drop for the heat exchanger
- < 10 bar for a shut-off valve
- < 10 bar for the break-away
- < 15 bar for the hose and piping parts
- < 10 bar for the nozzle/receptacle assembly
- < 85 bar for the TSTS

Of course, this repartition is an example and pressure drops can be split differently. However, it is important to keep in mind that just one component with poor performance will impact the whole line.

Upstream part: from high-pressure storages to PCV outlet

Figure 6 shows the results of the same refueling that on Figure 3, but using stations with increased pressure drops in its upstream part. On the left (a), pressure drops between storages and PCV outlet were doubled compared to the reference case⁷. It can seem a lot to double the reference pressure drop, however it can very easily be reached with longer or narrower pipes between storages and dispenser. On the right (b) is represented a refueling with a PCV used in current stations (made for 60 or 90 g/s 700 bar refueling instead of a high-flow PCV).

Figure 6 – Refueling simulation results – larger upstream pressure drops. Timescales of (a) and (b) are different. On the left (a), the refueling is in the same conditions as reference refueling except pressure drops are doubled (at the reference operating point). Final SOC is almost 98% and fueling time is 8 min and 5 sec. Fueling stops because there is no more pressure storage, however very close to pressure limit. On the right (b), the refueling is in the same conditions as reference refueling except pressure drops are strongly increased because a PCV currently used in existing stations is used. The reference operating point is not reachable. Final SOC is 57%, fueling stops because there is no available storage left after 4 min and 50 sec.

⁷ They are multiplied by two at the given reference conditions (200 g/s, 300 bar at PCV, 15°C). The ratio might then change depending on the operating point.

On the left, fueling is almost complete even with increased pressure drops. However, it can be seen that the last cascade is completely used while there is still some hydrogen left in the reference case. Thus, back-to-back refueling performance will be much lower with this configuration. Indeed, as for downstream pressure drops, **upstream pressure drops leads to higher needs in high pressure storage**. It is even more visible on the right, where pressure drops are even higher. Here, the cascade pressure needed for sufficient flow to follow approximately the ramp is way higher than the ramp pressure. With such pressure drop, only a small part of each cascade can be used. Consequently, cascades are used up faster, and very quickly, no cascade is available anymore. As previously, the impact of final SOC shown in these simulations depends on the exact chosen configuration and total hydrogen amount in storages. But in any case, more high-pressure capacity is needed for the same refueling when pressure drops are larger.

Note: Control strategy used here limits maximum difference between ramp pressure and real dispenser pressure. Other strategy can be to allow larger margin between ramp pressure and dispenser pressure. However, in these cases flow peaks can be observed when switching from a cascade to another (to “catch-up with the ramp pressure”). Such peaks could lead to overshoot the maximum limit of 300 g/s, which causes the refueling to stop. Control strategies must therefore prevent this to happen, for instance by forbidding too much discrepancy between ramp and dispenser pressure, or by opening progressively the path when new cascades are used to smoothen the peak.

Note: PCV lack of reactivity can also cause ramp deviation and flow peaks when switching cascades. Therefore, it is also very important to **ensure pressure control system is reactive enough**, by correctly choosing PCV, its controller, a correct air circuit design and appropriate control settings

Anyway, it is recommended to keep the pressure drops at their minimum. 70 bar of pressure drop when hydrogen flows at 200 g/s, 15°C and 300 bar at PCV is recommended by RHeaDHy project as a demanding but reachable target. For instance, pressure drop can be split among major components as:

- < 10 bar pressure drop for shut-off valve
- < 15 bar pressure drop for the flowmeter
- < 10 bar pressure drop for the fully opened PCV
- <35 bar pressure drop for cascades valves and piping from storages to dispenser

Once again, these values can be split differently. It can be noted that better valves performance will allow more piping pressure drop, which might be advantageous in sites where layout imposes large distances between storages and dispenser.

RHeaDHy project components, fueling lines, TSTS are designed to meet the pressure drop recommendations, and therefore allow to refuel entirely a 100 kg hydrogen system in less than 10 minutes with reasonable use of the high-pressure storages.

5.2 Allow state-of-the-art communication during refueling

Enabling more advanced communication is an important lever to increase safety and performance during refueling.

- It is recommended to **implement at least SAE J2799v2 [6], and to be able to receive FM and TVL in the OD field.**
- It is recommended to follow carefully the standards update and to **be ready to integrate bidirectional communication.**

Explanations:

Communication is an effective way to improve refueling performances. Next paragraphs will illustrate how the existence of communication between station and vehicle allow to improve performance in the existing protocols SAE J2601, SAEJ2601-5 and in PRHYDE protocol concepts.

In previous protocols such as categories A, B, C of SAEJ6201 [5], communication helped to improve the final SOC of the vehicle. Indeed, in such protocols, pressure targets are higher when communication is used compared to when it is not⁸. However, the fueling speed is the same. Consequently a communication refueling will last a bit longer than a non-communication refueling, but final SOC will be higher, which is very important for users.

With SAE J2601-5 protocols [4], communication can allow to improve SOC but also to reduce fueling time. Communication pressure target is still higher than non-communication pressure, so final SOC is also higher in refuelings using communications. Additionally, with these protocols and in particular the structuration of the OD field in communicated data, the use of communication can also help to improve the fueling time. It can be the case when:

- The vehicle sends its tank system total volume to the station using the communication field TV. Depending on its value, the flow-limiting APRR or PRR will evolve, and in MC-formula protocol TV value also determines the t_{final} table to use, therefore acting of the refueling velocity.
- The vehicle sends “FM = 90” in OD field to a compatible H70 dispenser with H70 coupling. Then the maximum flow limit is increased from 60 g/s to 90 g/s. In most cases, it leads to a refueling time reduction. For instance, for a 100kg system, at an ambient temperature of 15°C and an injection temperature of -30°C, fueling time can be estimated around 40 minutes using a maximum flow of 60 g/s while it is around 27 minutes with a maximum flow of 90 g/s.
- The vehicle sends its largest tank volume TVL to the dispenser in its OD field. If TVL is not in the maximum range possible, it will allow the dispenser to choose higher APRRs or smaller t_{final} s, leading to a faster refueling if the maximum flow is not already limiting the velocity.

For instance, the reference refueling presented on Figure 3 uses communication. To illustrate its importance, another refueling simulation is made in the same conditions but this time, without using any communication.

⁸ Communication pressure target are computed to limit the worst-case SOC to a value slightly higher than 100% (for instance 120% in table-based SAE J2601), because in normal cases refueling is stopped when the station reads that 100% SOC is reached thanks to the communicated values. In case of communication issue, the SOC won't exceed 120% which is considered as acceptable in case of problem (see A.3.13 of SAEJ2601 [5] for more detail)

Figure 7 – Refueling simulation results – no COM: the refueling is in the same conditions as the reference refueling except no communication is used. Final SOC is 86% and fueling time is 12 min and 15 sec.

It can be seen that this refueling without communication give poorer performance compared to the one with communication:

- Fueling time is longer: it takes four more minutes to finish the refueling, even if the final pressure is lower. This is because the t_{final} vector used was chosen using the most conservative t_{final} table while when TV is known via communication, the t_{final} vector corresponds exactly to the system volume (a bit below 2500L).⁹ Here, TVL is also communicated, but as it is in the most conservative range [350, 800L], knowing it do not improve fueling velocity.
- Final SOC is lower: it is 86% while it was 98% with communication. This is because the non-communication pressure limit is lower than communication pressure target / pressure limits.¹⁰

Finally, **innovative protocols will use future bi-directional communication to further improve both refueling time and final SOC**. For instance, in PRHYDE protocols, refueling process is quite similar to SAE J2601-5 MC formula protocol, but the main difference is that the t_{final} tables are communicated from the vehicle to the station at the beginning of the refueling. It allows to remove a lot of conservative hypotheses about the vehicle tank system, and therefore improving the fueling speed (see [3] for more detail). However, it means the fueling speed will be controlled by parameters coming from communication. To allow that, communication should improve its level of reliability. Future ISO 19885-2 standard will define more precisely communication requirements between vehicle and dispenser system for different UCDC levels.

⁹ Station measurement of the vehicle's tanks total volume during the refueling could be a way to improve non-communication refueling time. However, it adds complexity in protocol implementation, and it should be checked that the time spent to pause the fueling to measure volume and update parameters is not superior to the time gained when updating the t_{final} used afterwards

¹⁰ Here, pressure ending tables method is used to control the end of the refueling. Using MC-method to determine pressure target could help improve slightly final SOC, however it is still expected to be below communication final SOC

RHeaDHy project is planning to test advanced protocols as PRHYDE, first in a test environment with test field hardware communication allowing bi-directional communication, and possibly then with a prototype of advanced bi-directional communication hardware. Main test results and conclusions about the fueling performance improvement when using these advanced protocols will be communicated by the end of RHeaDHy project.

It can be concluded that it is strongly recommended to use communication in order to improve refueling performance. It is especially advised to use the OD field as defined in SAEJ2799v2 [6], and to be prepared to implement new bi-directional communication when standards and technical solutions will be available.

5.3 Use a flowmeter suitable for the dynamic process conditions covered by the refueling protocols

High-capacity hydrogen refueling systems experience dynamic processes. **When selecting a measurement flow meter for these systems it is recommended to keep several factors in mind:**

- **Measured variable output needed** for the HRS
- **Certification** accuracy requirement for HRS
- **Accuracy** of the flow meter across HRS flow ranges
- Pressure of HRS filling cycles
- Maximum allowable working pressure of flow meter
- Pressure cycling rating of flow meter
- Pressure drop across flow meter at HRS operating conditions
- Temperature behaviour of HRS and flow meter temperature specifications
- Density variation of the hydrogen throughout the transaction
- Space available for flow meter in HRS

Explanations:

As there are many different flow metering principles in the market, it is important to understand **which measuring principle can be used best for the application**, each measuring principle has its pro's and con's. For hydrogen fueling, **since transactions take place in kilograms, it is recommended to select a flow meter that measures mass directly and accurately.**

Since hydrogen refueling stations are used for sales transactions, potentially even direct sales to the public, **regulations and certifications are to be followed for both the flow meter as well as the complete HRS.** One aspect of this certification is proving the measurement accuracy of the flow meter across a defined range of flowrates. It is recommended to select a flow meter that has obtained, or is about to obtain, such type of approval certification. In this way, measurement accuracy of the flow meter is guaranteed.

The flow meter should also practically fit the application. In RHeaDHy project, a Coriolis flowmeter is developed by Emerson-Micromotion. As mentioned earlier, pressure drop is a crucial factor in (high flow) hydrogen refueling. Due to the nature of Coriolis meter measurement methods, Coriolis flow meters introduce a pressure loss across the sensor, commonly known as the pressure drop of the sensor. Therefore, it is recommended to **assess flow meter characteristics at the intended operational conditions when sizing a Coriolis flow meter.** A factor that plays a role in the pressure drop in combination with mass flow rate is the density. As the pressure in the line increases, the density of the fluid and the mass flow rate also increases. As the density changes, the velocity through the flow meter will change as well. Although significant velocities are allowed due to hydrogen properties, it is recommended to assess the maximum velocity through both the flow meter and HRS.

As hydrogen fuel stations in IDLE situations are typically at ambient conditions and transfers typically take place at temperatures between -20 and -40 degrees, the flow meter will undergo many of these temperature cycles. **The selected Coriolis sensor should be rated to the extremes of the operational temperature cycles, as well as maintain mass measurement performance across the temperature range.**

Process cycle considerations should also be made for the pressure in the flow meters. In IDLE, the sensor will experience ambient pressure conditions and throughout the hydrogen refueling process the pressure will vary and become significant. It is recommended to validate the flow meter design is capable of operating with these pressure variations. **The sensor should be rated to safely withstand the extreme pressure conditions without any additional measures and not have these influence the measuring results.** Additionally, specific to hydrogen refueling systems, the sensor should survive the intended pressure cycles inherent to refueling systems.

Finally, it is recommended to assess the flow meter process and mounting connections to guarantee an efficient method of both installing the flow meter and reducing the tension on the process connections.

5.4 Use indirect cooling systems with cold storage for efficiency and reliability

It is recommended to **minimize the installed chiller capacity of the cooling system to have an energy-efficient, compact and cost-effective system.** Therefore it is necessary to implement a **cold buffer** that can cover the short-term peak cooling duties and is being recharged by the chiller again during smaller cooling demand period or between two refuelings. This is a necessary condition for:

- Achieving compact dimensions of the system, especially low footprint
- Significantly reducing installed electrical power and power input of the system
- Avoiding part-load operation of the refrigeration compressor(s)

Explanations:

The approach of an indirect cooling system with a buffer storage module presents a highly efficient and reliable solution for the cooling of hydrogen dispensers at filling stations in the heavy-duty sector. Within the framework of the RHeaDHy project, this approach involves the combination of two chillers with a separate pump module and cold storage in a modular design that allows for high operational flexibility. The system can be operated with a single chiller, which is particularly important for service work, and can be expanded as needed or alternatively configured for maximum capacity from the outset. This scalability, combined with the existing redundancy of the two chillers and the separate cold storage module, ensures both operational reliability and adaptability to changing requirements.

A key advantage of this design lies in its **effective management of peak temperature loads, especially during the initial cooling phases. By integrating the separate cold storage module, the system can absorb temperature peaks that occur at the beginning of the filling process without needing to size the chillers for peak loads** (see example of typical cooling demand during refueling on Figure 8). This leads to a significant reduction in connection power, as the chillers can be designed based on average cooling demands, while the cold storage module handles temporary peak loads. This approach results in a more consistent operation of the chillers without performance spikes, which increases energy efficiency and extends the lifespan of the equipment. In the context of the RHeaDHy project, the chillers have a cooling capacity of 60 kW each and the overall system can cover a peak load of up to 310 kW of cooling power that's to the buffer use.

Figure 8 – Example of cooling capacity requirement during a high-flow refueling. The peak is covered by the cold accumulator while the refrigerating machine provides a continuous cooling capacity lower than the maximum cooling demand.

The use of a heat transfer medium in the indirect cooling system provides additional advantages in terms of system flexibility and stability. The thermal mass can be adjusted to meet the specific requirements of the application, enabling customized solutions. This adaptability contributes to a more stable system behavior, as thermal inertia dampens temperature fluctuations and ensures stable cooling processes. As a result, not only is the efficiency of the system increased, but its responsiveness to variable loads is also improved.

Therefore, **the combination of chillers and a cold storage secures consistent performance under varying loads, making the system particularly suitable for the cooling of hydrogen dispensers at filling stations in the heavy-duty sector.**

5.5 Optimize high-pressure storage capacity

High-pressure storage are costly, their footprint is non-negligible, and filling them requires energy for compression. Therefore, it is important to optimize the station storage dimensioning. Total number of high-pressure storage tanks and associated nominal working pressure are the first key variables to consider. However, at fixed number and NWP of storages, cascade configuration organization can also have a large impact.

To optimize the design at a given number of high-pressure tanks, it is recommended:

- To **limit pressure drops** in the whole station at a minimum (see part 5.1)
- To **split the number of storages in as much cascades as possible**, while keeping in mind that number of cascades switches¹¹ might be limited by the protocol.
- To **increase the number of banks at the end of the refueling** rather than at the beginning (at limited number of banks).

¹¹ To be more specific: the number of times the flow drops below a minimum value is often limited by the protocol. Most of the time, switching cascades leads to a decrease of the flow below this value.

Explanation:

To adapt both RHeaDHy test zones at HRS and ZBT sites, the project partners were confronted to the need of choosing between different cascades configuration possibilities. Layout and budget being constrained, the question of how to optimize cascade configurations at given number of storage tanks to maximize usable hydrogen was raised. The main findings were the following:

- It is better to split the storage in multiple banks to take benefits of the high-pressure.
- If the number of cascades is limited (by protocols, piping & valves cost, ...), it seems better to increase the number of cascades at the higher pressure level, to be used at the end of the refueling.

These guidelines can be illustrated using simulations. In Figure 3, the reference case uses a reference architecture. Here, a new storage architecture is created, with one pressure bank of NWP 500 bar with 152 kg and two pressure banks of NWP 950 bar with 160 kg each. This new storage configuration has the same total mass of hydrogen per pressure as the reference case, but it is split in less banks. Figure 9 shows a refueling with the new storage architecture, in the same refueling conditions than the reference refueling.

Figure 9 - Refueling simulation results – larger pressure banks: the refueling is in the same conditions as the reference refueling except cascades are reorganised. Here, one cascade of 152 kg at NWP = 500 bar and two cascades of 160 kg at NWP = 950 bar are used instead of two cascades of 76 kg at NWP = 500 bar and eight cascades of 40 kg at NWP = 950 bar. Final SOC is 94% and fueling time is 7 min and 40 sec.

The impact of organizing pressure storages in larger banks can be seen: the fueling stops at 7 minutes and 40 seconds because there is no more high-pressure storage available. Final SOC is 94%, so 4 percentage points less than in the refueling with the reference cascade configuration. This can be explained by the fact that to enable hydrogen to flow to the vehicle, the storage pressure must exceed the dispenser pressure. It means that even if a cascade still holds a large quantity of hydrogen, its usable mass might be very low or zero. It is the case here: at the end of the refueling, the large cascades of NWP=950 bar still hold large amounts of hydrogen but at pressures that are not exploitable to finish the fueling. Dividing such large banks into several smaller banks would allow for more efficient utilization of the higher pressures available. Of course, the impact of final SOC shown in these simulations is very dependent on the exact chosen configuration and total hydrogen amount in storages. However, the conclusion that **more high-pressure capacity is needed for the same**

refueling when cascades are larger is generic. Thus, it is recommended to optimize cascades arrangement in all stations, in order to increase refueling capacity (for one large vehicle or for back-to-back refuelings).

Two other configurations were also tested to show intermediary possibilities between reference case (Figure 3) and large cascades case (Figure 9). One increasing the number of cascades at the beginning of the refueling, the other increasing the number of cascades at the end.

Figure 10 - Refueling simulation results – larger pressure banks variations: the refueling is in the same conditions as the reference refueling except cascades are reorganised. On the left (a), one cascade of 152 kg at NWP=500 bar, one cascade of 160 kg at NWP = 950 bar, one cascade of 80 kg NWP = 950 bar and two cascades of 40 kg at NWP = 950 bar are used instead of two cascades of 76 kg at NWP = 500 bar and eight cascades of 40 kg at NWP = 950 bar. Final SOC is 97% and fueling time is 7 min and 55 sec. On the right (b), two cascades of 76 kg at NWP = 500 bar, two cascades of 40 kg at NWP = 950 bar and one cascade of 240 kg at NWP = 950 bar are used instead of two cascades of 76 kg at NWP = 500 bar and eight cascades of 40 kg at NWP = 950 bar. Final SOC is 94% and fueling time is 7 min and 40 sec.

It can be observed that when station hydrogen capacity split into 5 banks with smaller and more numerous cascades at the end of the refueling (a), final SOC is 97%. When the same capacity is split in 5 banks but this time with smaller and more numerous cascades at the beginning of the refueling, final SOC is 94%. Thus, it shows that increasing the number of banks at the end of the refueling is more efficient than increasing the number of banks at the beginning. This is because higher pressure demand is close to the end of the refueling: it is at this point it is most important to increase high-pressure availability by splitting into smaller banks. **Therefore, if the number of banks is limited (because of protocol, cost limit, control logic, ...), it is preferable to use the smallest banks at the end of the refueling.**

Note: it has been noticed that the advice of splitting the pressure banks as much as possible might be misleading in the case of relatively high lower pressure limits of the bank (the bank cannot be defueled more than a certain pressure). In that case, it might not be beneficial to increase the number of cascades at the beginning of the refueling, when the cascade use is limited by its minimum pressure limit and not by the pressure ramp.

Note: depending on piloting choices, using a very large number of cascades can also add some refueling time (by increasing the time spent to switch from one cascade to another).

Finally, when the station part linking pressure storage to dispenser is designed, high-flow station manufacturers should be careful about the pressure drops that are created by valves at the outlet of the storages and pipes from the cascades to the station. Indeed, outlet storages valves are sometimes small, and long distances between storages and dispenser might force to use long piping and lots of elbows, which can create non-negligible pressure drops when at high flow. Illustration of such pressure drops impact and recommendations of values to target are given in 5.1.

6 Recommendation for vehicles design

6.1 Minimize pressure drop from the receptacle to the tanks

It is recommended **to minimize pressure drop in the vehicle hydrogen line**, between the receptacle and the hydrogen tanks. To do so, all components and piping should be designed to allow high flow. This is a necessary condition for:

- Rapid refueling
- High State-of-charge at the end of the refueling
- Optimal use of high-pressure storage

It is recommended to target maximum 15 MPa of pressure drop in the entire hydrogen vehicle line when at 100 bar in the vehicle, - 15°C, with a flow of 200 g/s. ¹²

Explanations:

The rationale for limiting pressure drop from the receptacle to the tanks is the same than for limiting pressure drop between the pressure control valve and the nozzle (see part 5.1 – downstream pressure drops).

The specific value for pressure drop used in the recommendation given above comes from SAE J2601-5, section A.3.2.8. According to our simulations, these values are relevant to limit pressure drops and allow fast refueling with a satisfying final SOC. Moreover, it is practically possible to reach such pressure drop value when building a truck storage system (it will be done on RHeaDHy TSTS). In the gas industry it exists components with large channels allowing high Kv values. These designs could be adapted for mobility and validated according to ISO 19887-1 [7] but the cost versus performance parameter will be more challenging for mobility mass production than for industrial application. Thus, a careful design of the vehicle hydrogen line is necessary, with special attention on choosing components and piping diameter large enough for the pressure drop to be limited.

6.2 Implement state-of-the-art communication during refueling

As it was explained for the station, enabling more advanced communication is an important lever to increase safety and performance during refueling.

- It is recommended to **implement at least SAE J2799v2, and to communicate FM and TVL to the station in the OD field.**
- It is recommended to follow carefully the standards update and to **be ready to integrate bidirectional communication.**

¹² Receptacle excluded (receptacle pressure drop is taken into account “on station side” via pressure drops of the coupling nozzle / receptacle)

Explanations:

Communication should be applied on both dispenser and vehicle side. Part 5.2 details the benefits of communication during refueling.

6.3 Limit thermal stratification using appropriate design

In various external projects, partners have observed high stratification in tanks during refueling. This may lead to heat peaks at some places of the tank, and possible local hotspot even with a far lower average temperature. Stratification also depends on the vertical or horizontal positioning of the tank.

It is therefore **recommended to limit thermal stratification**, thanks to:

- Geometrical considerations (for instance, aspect ratio has an important impact on temperature development during refueling)
- Injector size, positioning and orientation

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) modelling and real testing with multiple temperatures sensors are also highly recommended to ensure there is no heating pockets when refueling the tank.

Explanations:

One of the main use of a refueling protocol is to limit the temperature increase due to gas compression below 85°C. However, it must be underlined that all the existing refueling protocols are developed with 0D/1D models computing the average gas temperature, based on the assumption that the hydrogen temperature in the tanks is close to homogeneous.

However, it has been found that this assumption is not always verified. For instance, during PRHYDE project testing, thermal differences as high as 27°C were observed between the hotter and the colder measurement point as shown on Figure 13. These temperatures were measured thanks to a thermocouple tree with multiple thermocouples dispatched in the tank, and are considered to be fairly representative of the range of temperatures present in the tank. (see [3]).

Figure 11 - Taken from PRHYDE report [3]: Temperatures measured by thermocouple tree sensors during refueling and following standby, showing large temperature heterogeneities.

The European project HyTransfer also studied this issue [8]. Both HyTransfer and PRHYDE projects state that further investigation on this temperature heterogeneity issue is important, whether to understand its occurring conditions better or to take it into account while deriving hydrogen refueling protocols.

Therefore, it is essential to think the design of tanks and injectors to limit stratifications and hot spots. Experimental testing and CFD simulations can help ensuring a specific design. It should be noted that CFD models should be validated against experimental data in similar conditions to which they will be used. Indeed PRHYDE project work showed that depending on mesh and turbulence model chosen, the results of a CFD simulation can be completely different (see [3], parts 9.3 and 10.2.2). It is therefore important to ensure that the choices made are relevant before using the CFD results to make design decisions (see example of Forvia thermal simulations on tanks on Figure 12).

In RHeaDHy, Forvia is well aware of such problematics. Forvia studied and designed carefully its tanks and injectors to limit stratification during refuelings, and consequently to avoid hotspots and hot pockets onset. Moreover, TSTS design includes the same tank positioned horizontally and vertically to be able to compare temperature evolution.

Figure 12 - Thermal gas mapping at end of refueling (example simulations done by Forvia, not representative of RHeaDHy tanks) - From left to right and top to bottom: Vertical tank with injection by the top / Vertical tank with injection by the bottom / Horizontal tank with injection toward the top / Vertical tank with injection toward the bottom. Scale limited to 85°C, hot spot > 85°C

6.4 Ensure representative temperature measurement

In various external projects, partners have observed some issues with tank temperature sensor placement. It lead to a measured temperature in tank corresponding to the cold inlet temperature and not to the average or maximum heating in the tank.

It is therefore **recommended to study carefully temperature sensor placement: not in hydrogen flux, but in a location with representative temperature.** CFD study with validated models can help to locate the sensor in a relevant way.

If possible, it is also **recommended to use multiple sensors at different locations in the tanks if possible,** in order to have multiple measurements and increase measure reliability.

Explanations:

In their previous experiences, RHeaDHy partners had observed at several occasions non-representative measurements of the hydrogen tank temperature during refueling. Thus, the temperature measured at the OTV can be impacted by the pre-cooled hydrogen entering the tank, and therefore not represent anymore the average gas temperature. And most hydrogen tanks use only this temperature sensor to get the tank temperature. Some examples of this issue are given in PRHYDE report and shown here on Figure 13:

Figure 13 – Taken from PRHYDE report [3]: Temperature evolution measured during some of the PRHYDE refueling tests, for two different OTV-tank combination.

Here on the left graph, it can be seen that the OTV temperature is approximately the average temperature measured by the thermocouple tree (considered as a good approximation of the average hydrogen temperature in the tank given the number and location of thermocouples, see [3]). It means the OTV temperature is representative of the average temperature. But on the right graph, it can be seen that the OTV temperature is rather following the dispenser pre-cooled hydrogen temperature, and not the average temperature measured by the thermocouple tree.

Not having a good estimate of the temperature of the tank can have multiple consequences, especially for communication refuelings where the temperature is communicated from the vehicle to the dispenser. In particular, it can lead to a wrong estimation of the vehicle SOC, or lead to an undetected overheating – especially in some protocols like PRHYDE TgasThrottle.

In RHeaDHy, this issue was seriously considered. Forvia studied and designed carefully its tank/OTV assembly and positioning of the temperature sensor to ensure they do not measure the inlet gas temperature. RHeaDHy is confident the temperature measurements in the TSTS will be relevant, based on Forvia previous experience and CFD simulations.

6.5 Develop common connections design

Today, it has been observed a large variety of high pressure line connections for mobility and vehicle tank system design. **Having a common design supported by a normative document (for instance ISO) would bring better interchangeability and reliability to connections.**

Explanations:

Today, a plurality of connection types are used in truck storage systems. For instance, cone to cone connections, cone to sphere connections, double ferrule connections can be used.

	SUPPLIER A 700bar	SUPPLIER B 700bar	SUPPLIER C 700bar	SUPPLIER D 700bar	SUPPLIER E 700bar
With Female nut					
With Male nut				NO	NO

Figure I4 - Metal to metal sealing interface

	SUPPLIER A 350bar	SUPPLIER B 350bar	SUPPLIER C 700bar
With Female nut			
With fittings			

Figure I5 - O-ring face seal interface

	SUPPLIER A 700bar	SUPPLIER B 350bar	SUPPLIER C 350bar	SUPPLIER D 350bar	SUPPLIER E 350bar	SUPPLIER F 350bar
With fittings						

Figure I6 - Double ferrule sealing interface

Not having a common design can lead to very poor interchangeability of connections. This might be problematic when looking to improve a design, especially to build high flow storage systems where it is crucial to choose appropriated components and limit the number of connections and adapters. The lack of common design supported by normative document is also detrimental for connection reliability. Thus, it would benefit the whole industry to converge on a common design.

7 Recommendations for high-flow refueling protocols development

7.1 Describe very precisely protocols in pseudo-code to facilitate implementation

While improving to allow fastest and safe refueling for a wider range of vehicles, refueling protocols are also becoming more and more complex. However, they need to be implemented correctly and consistently in each dispenser applying them to ensure safety and performance and to help the industry gain confidence in refueling capacities.

We recommend that every standardized protocol is explicitly described, explained and detailed as much as possible in “pseudo-code”, so that its implementation does not leave room for interpretation nor for misunderstanding errors.

Explanations:

Refueling protocols are responsible for avoiding overheating, overfilling or over-pressurization of the vehicle tanks that are being refueled, to prevent any damage to these tanks. Therefore, it is crucial these protocols are correctly implemented, in order to ensure to prevent exceeding pressure or temperature limits.

Hence, it seems very important to RHeaDHy project members to have standardized protocols that are implemented in the same way in all stations using them. We believe it is necessary that as much detail as possible is given when a protocol is published, as **detailing a protocol steps and equations clearly will accelerate its implementation process and limit the possible programming errors**. Especially, it is important to state:

- *Rationale*: explaining how the protocol works and the use of each step will allow station manufacturers, operators, truck manufacturers and truck owners to understand and trust it. It can also allow to make informed choices about the protocol's options, if any. It is not advised to have “black box” protocols whose functionalities and limitations are harder to understand and might lead to misuse.
- *Range of validity*: it is extremely important to state clearly the validity range and hypotheses taken for protocol derivation. It will allow to ensure station and truck manufacturers that their equipment can indeed use the protocol safely.
- *Parameters*: the meaning of each parameter and its unit should be specifically detailed, in order to avoid any misunderstanding that may lead to implementation errors.
- *Steps sequence*: the order of the protocol steps and the transition conditions to one step to another should be clearly stated, once again to avoid misunderstandings leading to implementation errors.
- *Pseudo-code of the protocol with detailed equations*: The more detailed the protocol, the easier to encode it without errors or misunderstanding, and therefore the safer.

Thus, having this level of detail and transparency will have lots of benefits. We believe it is **key to increase protocol adoption - as it will appear easy and quick to implement by station manufacturers- and key to ensure its proper implementation, thus the refueling reliability and safety**.

7.2 Develop methods and tools to check correct implementation

As explained previously, protocols are becoming more and more complex and they need to be implemented correctly and consistently in each dispenser to ensure safety and performance and to help the industry gain confidence in refueling capacities. In addition to making them as explicit as possible, we recommend:

- To **build publicly-available tools helping to check if a protocol is correctly implemented** in a station
- To **have a list of tests and acceptance criteria** to validate the refueling protocol implementation and the communication ability implementation.

Explanations:

As detailed in part 7.1, correct implementation of protocols is key to avoid overheating, overfilling and over-pressure. Therefore, in addition to detailing the protocol rationale and equations, we believe that it is important to **give clear means of checking protocols are correctly implemented in the station and apply the adequate control.**

For instance, it is recommended that the hydrogen mobility industry:

- **Develop free public tools helping to check if a protocol is correctly implemented** in the stations. Such tools can already be found for SAE J2601 and are being developed for SAE 2601-5. We believe such tools are very valuable for industry as it can quickly help dispenser manufacturers to validate the protocol is programmed correctly, or help find errors and debug the program if necessary. Having such a tool for each high-flow protocol development will therefore increase protocol adoption as it makes the validation process faster and easier.
- **Agree on a standardized list of tests for dispenser validation of fueling protocol and vehicle-station communication**, for instance to be implemented during FAT and SAT. For light-duty vehicle refuelings, ISO 19880-1 [9] already describes in an informative annex some recommended tests to validate SAE J2601 (2016 version) and SAE J2799 (2014 version). We believe the same kind of document should be agreed on for each new high-flow protocol. In particular, it should describe tests that ensure:
 - Dispenser reacts correctly to process limit violations and to stop requests.
 - Protocol control parameters are correctly implemented and used.
 - Refueling protocol performance meets expectations.
 - Communication is correctly managed: data is received and interpreted as it should, and in particular the dispenser response to out of bound or badly formatted data is adequate.

Clear test definition and acceptance criteria should be defined to check for each above point.

Once again, such measures **seem key to increase stakeholder confidence in protocol implementation and therefore to increase protocol adoption, and consequently develop high-flow refueling.**

7.3 Focus on testing and improving existing protocols or protocols already well-advanced in their development

As shown above, SAE J2601-5 protocol (MC-formula, FM300) already give very satisfying performances for large heavy-duty refueling. Other protocols already well-advanced in development, as PRHYDE ones, can further improve it by removing some conservative hypotheses.

Therefore, we **recommend to focus on testing, improving and disseminating existing protocols** rather than developing a lot of brand-new approaches which will add complexity but not necessarily lead to a significant performance gain.

Explanations:

High flow protocols already available (SAE J2601-5) or already precisely drafted (PRHYDE) are expected to give very good performance:

- Main refueling time inferior to 10 minutes for heavy-duty trucks as large as 100 kg, with - 30°C precooling temperature
- Final SOC generally between 95 and 100%.

As the performance of such protocols is already very satisfying, RHeaDHy believes the **main efforts to deploy about protocols is in:**

- **Testing:** Extensive high-flow protocols testing should be realized in many different situations (various stations configuration, vehicle configurations, initial and ambient parameters, ...) to enhance confidence in protocol and to ensure they work as expected to limit overheating and overpressure.
- **Improving:** To improve safety, performance or to simplify it, protocol updates can be conducted while keeping the same core logic. Thus, slight improvements can be conducted
- **Supporting their implementation:** Dissemination about the protocols capabilities and advantages can help speed up its adoption. As mentioned in 7.2, the development of validation tools and standards is also a good mean to facilitate protocol implementation. Finally, during the first years of use, communication between stakeholders should be facilitated so that questions, uncertainties or possible identified issues can be addressed commonly.

Additionally, the **development effort for high-flow components** should continue, to enable real 300 g/s refueling not limited by pressure drops and to reduce high-flow station costs.

This seems to us higher priority than developing completely new protocols approaches. Indeed, **having too much different protocols can lead to far more complexity**, especially:

- Additional workload and therefore additional costs. Indeed, having more protocols to understand, implement, validate on each dispenser (and possibly on each truck for protocols using bi-directional communication) will lead to a significant amount of additional work, thus leading to higher costs.
- Possible compatibility issues. If a lot of very different protocols are available, it is possible dispenser manufacturers or truck manufacturers decide to implement only some of them. This might lead to non-compatible couples truck-dispenser, with no common refueling protocol. In this case, refueling will either be impossible or will be conducted with non-communication protocol leading to poorer performance.

8 Attention points for the hydrogen mobility industry

8.1 Test all equipment for leaks with hydrogen, including with temperature gradients that will be seen during operation

In order to avoid hydrogen leaks and associated risks, diligent leak tests should be done. In particular, it is recommended:

- To **test for leaks with Hydrogen** gas and not with other gases as Argon or Nitrogen.
- To **test for leaks while applying dynamic temperature variations the component will see during its normal use** (for instance, for components used in refueling stations or vehicles fueling line: apply dynamic temperature ramp-down from ambient down to -30°C in around 30 s, with pressures similar to the refueling pressures.).

Explanations:

During previous test campaigns, RHeaDHy partners were confronted multiples times with the following two situations on different material:

- First, some components had been tested for leaks with gases as Nitrogen or Argon, and were found leak-proof with such gases. However, when used with hydrogen, leakage appeared.
 - Therefore, it is strongly advised to test all hydrogen components with hydrogen at least for the leak tests, as testing with other gases does not appear sufficient.
- Also, significative leakage has been observed on components while subject to a temperature gradient (from ambient to refueling precooling temperature). It appeared on components already tested with hydrogen and tested at cold static temperatures. Therefore, it was concluded that applying dynamic temperature constraint probably has an impact on some component parts behavior, leading to leaks.
 - Therefore, it is highly recommended to test all hydrogen components that will be subject to temperature gradients according to similar temperature gradients, and not only with static tests.

In RHeaDHy project, safety is a crucial concern. Special attention will be drawn in detecting leaks, both during initial components testing and during the main test campaign. Mitigation measures and actions to take are being decided to know how to react if leaks appear during the test campaign in spite of the preliminary testing and efforts to avoid them.

8.2 Need for testing facilities allowing high-flow testing in hydrogen

Facing the need to test its innovative components, RHeaDHy project was confronted to the lack of test facilities. More precisely, **two main issues were identified:**

- **Insufficient testing facilities using hydrogen, especially for leak test and cycling.**
- **Insufficient facilities with high-flow testing capacity**

RHeaDHy consortium believes development of testing facilities with hydrogen and high-flow is key to allow reliable hydrogen components to be developed quickly.

Explanations:

While developing station components or TSTS, RHeaDHy faced the need of testing its equipment to be sure it can be used safely during the test campaign. However, it was sometimes challenging to identify satisfying test facilities.

- The first need faced was to do *cycling and leak tests with hydrogen*. Indeed, as explained above, a component can leak with hydrogen even if it appears leak-proof with nitrogen or argon. Therefore, it is crucial to be able to test all components with hydrogen in their operating conditions. As mentioned above, being able to apply varying temperatures with hydrogen would also be very interesting to ensure the absence of leakage.
- The second need faced was the ability to *test components under high-flow*. Indeed, the high-flow effect on components is not yet well understood: is there any additional risks for components? does equipment wear more quickly, and to what extent? More reliable data is based on experimental information is needed to answer this question. Therefore, facilities able to test at high-flow (up to 300 g/s) in pressure and temperature conditions are needed, including facilities able to test large tanks behavior.
- Finally, even if *performance testing* can be done with other liquids or gases and then converted into hydrogen performance thanks to calculations, it is more direct and reliable to test it directly to hydrogen. For instance, it has been observed non-negligible uncertainties about hydrogen pressure drop calculation on a large range of flow using a flow coefficient “kv” measured on other gases.

RHeaDHy partners sometimes struggled to find facilities able to conduct such tests on individual components or sub-assemblies before assembling them into the dispenser or TSTS. Thus, this lack of facilities can lead to delays in hydrogen projects, or to the need of multiplying additional studies (theoretical, modelling works, risk studies) to ensure this lack of testing will not be problematic nor unsafe.

Therefore, we believe the development of hydrogen testing facilities is key to unlock the development of trusted components, and as such it should be developed by the hydrogen ecosystem.

8.3 Avoid use of calibrated orifices if possible

Calibrated orifices sometimes present to limit the flow at the maximum flow in case of sharp rupture of fueling line can be very detrimental for refueling performances. Therefore **it is not recommended to put calibrated orifices in hydrogen stations when legally and technically possible if – and only if - other mitigation measures are proved as valuable to limit maximum flow in case of critical event.** Such other mitigation measures should be studied by the industry and advocate towards regulation body in order to acknowledge their efficiency.

Explanations:

Calibrated orifices can significantly impact station performances. For instance, if an orifice is to be installed to limit flow to 300 g/s when high-pressure storages are full and are directly connected with ambient pressure at their output, the orifice will drastically limit the flow in normal refueling situations. Actually, it will lead to more pressure drops than what is shown on Figure 6 – Refueling simulation results – larger upstream pressure drops. Timescales of (a) and (b) are different. On the left (a), the refueling is in the same conditions as reference refueling except pressure drops are doubled (at the reference operating point). Final SOC is almost 98% and fueling time is 8 min and 5 sec. Fueling stops because there is no more pressure storage, however very close to pressure limit. On the right (b), the refueling is in the same conditions as reference refueling except pressure drops are strongly increased because a PCV currently used in existing stations is used. The reference operating point is not reachable. Final SOC is 57%, fueling stops because there is no available storage left after 4 min and Figure 6b (where final SOC is only 57%) Therefore, station high pressure capacity would need to be strongly increased to be able to finish the refueling, or fueling duration would have to be significantly extended. Both solutions are not very satisfying in terms of cost or performance.

Thus, it seems interesting that the rationale for choosing to integrate or not a calibrated orifice in the design considers that:

- With the component stations intrinsic pressure drops, maximum flow is already quite limited. Possible orifice dimensioning can be done by checking where ruptures are possible and by taking into account pressure drops due to existing piping, valves, instrumentation, ...
- Risk probability of such ruptures should be evaluated carefully given current trucks and station features, and given the presence of a break-away to control the fueling line rupture in case the vehicle manages to drive away while still attached to the hose.

9 Conclusion

Since the beginning of the project, RHeaDHy specified and designed components and refueling line capable of reaching 300 g/s and of refueling with high-flow protocols. From their past experience and from these first steps of specification, design and test preparation, RHeaDHy partners gained a better understanding of high-flow refueling. **Some main guidelines, attention points and findings to enable high-flow refueling have been summarized below** as recommendations for the hydrogen mobility ecosystem:

- **Pressure drops should be reduced as much as possible both on station side and on vehicle side**, to allow fast refueling, high final state-of-charge and to minimise high-pressure storage use.
- More precisely, **all components in high-flow stations should be designed specifically for high-flow refueling**. In addition to having low pressure drops, they must be suited for the high-flow refueling process. For instance, the ramp rate control should be designed so that it is reactive and accurate enough at such high-flow. Flowmeter must be suitable for all dynamic conditions that will occur during high-flow refueling, and be accurate enough on the wide range of hydrogen density, pressure, temperature, flow it will see. Cooling system design should be thought to minimize electrical consumption while ensuring performance.
- **Communication between station and vehicle during refueling should be implemented**. Today, optional data to communicated in SAE J2601-5 (TVL, FM) can allow to significantly reduce refueling time. Tomorrow, bi-directional communication could further increase performance and safety of refueling, by allowing some new protocols as PRHYDE ones to be implemented.
- **Temperature evolution in vehicle tanks during refueling should be carefully studied and measured**. In order to avoid overheating, thermal heterogeneities should be limited via judicious tank and injector design, and temperature measurement sensor(s) should be positioned thoughtfully in order to be representative of the bulk temperature.
- **Hydrogen refueling protocols should be described precisely. It is recommended to have some shared tools to check their implementation**. Having a high level of detail and transparency is key to increase protocol adoption and proper implementation, thus to ensure the refueling reliability and safety. It is also recommended to focus on spreading and improving existing high-flow protocols rather than developing new approaches with no significant performance gain.
- **Hydrogen testing facilities should be developed, to allow hydrogen leak tests and high-flow tests more easily**. Indeed, it is sometimes challenging to find appropriate testing infrastructure for new hydrogen products, which can slow the adoption of hydrogen solutions.

During the next two years, RHeaDHy will install and test two refueling lines with the two test storage truck systems. The extensive test campaign will bring a lot of concrete insights on the functioning, advantages and limits of high-flow refueling stations and protocols. Therefore, by the end of the project, **a second report will complement this one to specify and update the recommendations based on future test results**.

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